

E-government in Public Services

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ABSTRACT: The main objective of e-government is to reduce bureaucracy, provide a framework for debate and decision on the main initiatives, measures and projects on debureaucratization and ensure coherence in the implementation of the e-government policy proposal. Among the objectives of e-government we mention: increasing the cost efficiency and cost-effectiveness of the public services, provided ensuring access to official information through WEB pages, optimizing the use of material and human resources, as well as the time required to provide services providing public services through electronic means for citizens and the business environment, improving relations between the public sector and citizens, simplification of administrative procedures improving public services, development of state information infrastructure. There are many supports for electronic administration. We often think first of the Internet (web services on a computer or mobile phone), but an eGovernment project can rely on any form of telematics, such as near field communication (NFC), Bluetooth and/or radio-frequency identification (RFID) technology, as well as electronic voting procedures, or even video surveillance, which can converge with data processing, database building and biometric facial recognition methods. The term "e-government" emerged around the 1990s with the advent of the Internet. (Castells 2000, 372). In 1998, the launch in France of the government's action programme for the information society is characteristic of the launch of a national drive to develop e-government.

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This article falls into both the field of administrative sciences and the field of information and communication sciences. Thus, I begin by pointing out that in the early 2000s in OECD countries, the development of Internet access and the digital divide was one of the obstacles to the development of the use of e-government services online (Cole 2000, 329). In order to achieve the best results, dematerialization cannot be limited to the computerization of 'paper' procedures, which have their own logic (the culture of documents or form rather than data), a history that has often been constrained is accumulated over time to meet control needs and are therefore complex and designed for administration rather than for the user. An eGovernment project must therefore allow for a complete review of administrative procedures: the issue at stake is not so much how such a form or supporting document should be transmitted but why it should be and whether such transmission is useful and/or efficient. This is why, beyond the technical and IT issues, eGovernment generally leads to a thorough reorganization of the administration and its information system and its relations with other organizations and only yields very convincing results when it is a tool for this change and not an end in itself.

The process should include a pre-analysis, an implementation analysis and a post-analysis. The challenges will be 'internal' or 'external', depending on the breadth of vision of the person responsible for eGovernment. This is more than an intellectual exercise, as it determines how eGovernment integrates with the rest of the administration and meets the needs of citizens, businesses, and civil society. This broader governance issue is what is meant by the term 'eGovernment', but it is not unique to eServices and eConsultation. In the first phase of implementation, different organizations tended to respond to e-government requests by putting existing information online. For example, in terms of information provision, users can read and download publications, as well as conduct limited searches and queries (Chadwich and Nowars 2009). All information flows from administration to user. As this stage mainly involves digitizing existing data and putting it online, it has so far not required investment in process re-engineering and could therefore be achieved with minimal

planning. As countries implement more advanced services, they face a number of new, more challenging issues. The use of new technologies reveals the inconsistencies of rigid traditional systems. So there is a need not only to strengthen coordination and collaboration but also to reconfigure systems. Innovations will take place in a context of higher standards, less autonomy, and tighter controls. This will be beneficial for some public bodies but may be disappointing for others. (Chadwich, Digital Network Repertoires and Organisational Hybridity 2007, 283-301). E-Government is a clear priority for OECD countries, but to what extent are the lessons learned in these countries applicable to non-OECD countries? The answer is quite positive. While the questions of scope, approach, and level of technology must be decided by each country according to its own needs, the essential cultural change in public administration presents the same challenges for all countries. In fact, those who are in the process of acquiring a public service may benefit to the extent that they can incorporate new models of governance, particularly in their public service and legal systems, rather than trying to reinvent old models (Conroy, Feezell and Guerrero 2012).

The significant management issues presented by integrated service delivery show that the blurring of the line between roles and functions (due to information sharing and task shifting) makes it much more difficult to identify responsibilities within government. Before adopting highly sophisticated public management models, countries should ensure that they have a sufficient number of well-trained public sector managers. This ability to recruit, train and retain leaders and talent in the public sector - not technology - will determine the success of e-government initiatives. Good people are needed to ensure good governance of ICT investments. External consultants are an important means of bringing in specialist project management skills, but countries need to establish how they can maintain their capacity within the public sector to manage the resulting information imbalance. Development models for public-private partnerships and risk-sharing, breaking down silos or measures taken to prevent them from occurring, and maintaining transparency and accountability are some of the issues facing governments. (Nitschke and Donges 2016)

E-government is also about change and so far much progress has been made in e-government due to the enthusiasm of stakeholders. However, changes can occur against great resistance, especially when the implementation of integrated online services allows for the changes needed to achieve efficiency gains and significant service improvements. While the type of change and arrangements adopted depend on the specific political and administrative framework of each country and will continue to evolve to take account of lessons learned from experience, *leadership* is an essential ingredient of e-government capable of motivating agents and removing barriers to change. (Mueller 1992).

Decentralization has been a key element of public sector reforms in most OECD member countries over the past 20 years. The nature of e-government requires a degree of cooperation to assume interoperability, avoid duplication, ensure coherence of action in a number of key areas such as security and privacy, and provide the framework and resources for integrated services. The need for coordination will become even more acute as OECD member countries develop more complex transactional services. (Hagel and Brown 2002, 118). This makes e-government a dilemma at a central level. As the Finnish Council of Ministers said: "A fundamental issue is maintaining the responsibility and autonomy of the different bodies in terms of results and cooperation, while at the same time taking care of the interests of the public administration as a whole in terms of "interoperability and sharing of information resources". This goes back to the wider issue of coordination and decentralized management, but for eGovernment to be successful, it is essential to get the balance right. More control is tighter, and costs will be higher because of all the regulations and requirements that need to be met. Coordination can stifle innovation and initiative, leading to lost opportunities. However, a coordinated approach can lead to efficiency gains, reduce risks and facilitate initiatives.

Interdepartmental structures can play an important role in defining the framework for collaboration between organizations and ensuring that eGovernment activities are consistent with other programs. Central coordination units may be responsible for promoting the development of eGovernment across government, developing strategies, monitoring progress towards objectives, promoting the benefits derived from them with the public, linking activities with wider objectives and generally building and maintaining momentum. This may also include preparing progress reports and reassessing strategies against experience as progress is made. As mentioned earlier, integrated service is fast becoming a key issue for the implementation of user-oriented e-government. To do this, it is necessary to go beyond the coordination stage and integrate certain structures and processes related to service delivery. The experience gained during the implementation of integrated e-services has shown the effects this can have on the working methods, structures and culture of public bodies. The problems presented by the creation and operation of integrated services also highlight the need to change the internal governance frameworks of public administrations. Agreements to reconcile administrative management systems and an integrated customer interface may give the impression that this is only a technical issue and that other operations do not need to be changed. In practice, it will probably be different. Establishing integration models for online services will require a high degree of cooperation in architecture, service delivery policies and standards, and methods and programs. This will affect budgets, activities, skills, and resource management in general. Online services require deeper collaboration on issues such as service quality, data presentation, individual decision-making, problem-solving, complaints, and appeals. This will affect working methods, power transfers, and other aspects of organizational change. In general, service delivery policies using the full range of means used for this purpose will need to be defined and co-ordinated by organizations dealing with different customer groups (providing an integrated online service, leaving other means for lack of co-ordination is of little interest.) Integrated service delivery will increase the pressure for co-ordinated policies covering different customer groups and involving closer collaboration.

The rapid technological progress of recent years has also led to a considerable change in the methods and processes of working in education (Rotaru 2016, 326-334), while at the same time changing the perception of 'traditional' and 'modern'. Thus, teaching methods that were considered 'modern' a few years ago may now be classed as traditional, and the place of the modern has been taken by the new generation of methods, such as those of the digital age, which are constantly being improved and spread.

Only a few decades ago, digitization was talked about as a desirable field, somewhere far in the future. Nowadays, thanks to the global innovative effort and the efforts made to access new acquisitions, we can talk about digital systems in the field of education not only at international level, but also about their implementation in our country, as well as the domestic production of educational software.

Traditional methods, compared to digital ones, may seem outdated and inefficient, but they have been the basis for the development of new interactive methods (Rotaru 2011, 5-10). Thus we can say that methods centred on individual learner activity (textbook work, discovery learning, exercise) are the forerunners of contemporary methods of individual work with the tablet, for documentation purposes or for practicing new skills. Problem-solving and role-playing can also be used in interactive activities and form the basis of very modern digital methods.

Through digitization, accounting has a high chance of becoming one of the top outsourcing services thanks to the high degree of efficiency within the companies that use them. Administrative activities will be reduced. Therefore financial or human resources will be reduced, and at the same time, the error rate will decrease, and transparency will increase at the organizational level (Project co-financed by the European Social Fund through the Sectoral Operational Programme for Human Resources Development, 2013).

In the corporate risk management services that companies provide, clients' attention is drawn to the risks of the business, determining the level of acceptable risk, control methods are implemented, risk factors are monitored and assessed, and the rules in force are complied with.

Although this has been discussed for some time, services of this nature were not considered before the economic crisis. Over the last few years, thanks to the success of similar projects and the financial constraints companies have been under, interest in IT services has been growing. At the same time, more and more companies offering full IT services have emerged.

According to research, investment in IT services will increase in the coming years. In other words, IT outsourcing specialists are taking over more and more of the problems and tasks of the company's IT department, offering benefits in terms of day-to-day business, cost benefits and supporting companies' core business at a higher level.

The advantages, in this context, are outlined by a complete package of personalised services, undertaken by experienced specialists in the field, a low-cost package and free of the multitude of job interviews.

The projects established transnational partnerships and exchanges of good practice between public authorities, service providers and other actors from different cultural backgrounds, operating in different administrative and legal contexts and in different socio-economic environments. All projects emphasized the relevance of user involvement, on the one hand in defining and on the other in assessing the quality of social services.

The financial and economic crisis has had a significant impact on the public sector because of the pressure on public finances and it is important to make every effort to maintain the provision of these services and to improve their quality. In the coming months, the European Commission will undertake a number of other actions that will provide the European Union with a quality-based framework for services of general interest for the coming years. The European Commission will take this forward as part of its commitment to put social innovation and the social economy at the heart of the actions developed under the Europe 2020 strategy, in the same way as it has recently demonstrated its own social entrepreneurship initiative, which supports the evolution of innovative and new means of social entrepreneurship through economic activity and service provision.

Public service is identified in the method of administration through which services of general interest are provided to citizens under the regime of political power. The establishment of public services is the exclusive responsibility of local councils and deliberative authorities, while their structuring and operation is the responsibility of the executive authorities, i.e. mayors.

Big disruptors like Facebook, Amazon, and WhatsApp have revolutionized consumer behavior and put the customer first. Customer behavior and preferences are constantly changing; nowadays, a website showcasing a company in the digital realm is not enough. Social media and open source platforms such as blogs and websites are strengthening the customer's position as an opinion maker. Disruptors act very quickly. Once they enter the market, it will not be long before the business suffers. That is why it is advisable to identify it early to take the necessary measures. Accurately recognizing a disruptor before it becomes one is difficult. There are, however, marks left behind that can be noticed:

- It is inferior compared to the alternatives;
- It initially targets a small niche market and a specific audience;
- The target audience does not attract potential operators because of low margin and low revenue;
- It is created by foreigners from other industries;
- One or more advantages for the new user: ease of use, simplicity, low price, convenience (Colon 2016, 188).

There are four stages of the Big Bang Disruption:

1. Singularity - Despite stable supply chains, mature industries are becoming increasingly threatened by pressure from new entrants using disruptive technologies. Disruptors emerge first, with failed experiments taking place directly in the market. These tests are a signal of change in the making, and generally belong to innovators outside the industry that your business is targeting. In singularity the vision of the future needs to be a much clearer one to be able to identify the early warning signs of the arrival of disruptive change from outside your industry. Once identified, new ways of operating can be adopted.

2. The Big Bang - The right combination of technology and business model creates new markets characterized by rapid customer adoption across all segments. They are disrupting existing industries by abandoning old services and immediately tackling new ones. Old industries implode, then rebuild in a new but more unstable form. At this stage you need to be prepared for the sudden shift in customer orientation towards newer services and the winner-take-all markets created by disruptors.

3. The Big Crisis - As fast as markets are being cornered, the Big Bang Disruptors are being extinguished. Their implosion occurs considerably faster because the immediate adoption of their services by buyers leads to the saturation of markets in a very short time. The disruptor reaches its mature state, innovation becomes minor and the pace of growth slows. During the Great Depression, the industry experiences a kind of death, like the value created during the demise of the Big Bang. Those who stay in business too long quickly lose value. It is important to know here when is the right time to retire products and services in anticipation of disruptive change, no matter how profitable those goods are.

4. Entropy - Entropy represents the final stage in the death of industry, but also the stage at which the ground is prepared to re-enter the Singularity by creating something new from the remains of old goods. There may be eccentric customers who don't want to break away from the past and form a small launch market. The remaining assets, including intellectual property, can be put to new uses or form the basis for new incarnations of the business. (Tessi and Andreson 2015, 196-197). A different strategic approach to traditional wisdom is needed to stay in business, and authors Larry Downes and Paul Nunes highlight the differences between traditional and Big Bang wisdom in terms of strategy, marketing and innovation. We note that the disruptor who dominates the Big Bang wisdom is the one who believes in using all available possibilities, including non-digital tools. However, he understands that the pace of change in people's behavior is driven by technology evolving impressively fast. Geoffrey Colon, a social data expert at Microsoft, has identified four key skills of a disruptor, namely: 1. Always listen. 2. Do not be lured by bright, shiny objects. 3. Give back: ethics as the new marketing 4. Learn, unlearn, relearn.

Conclusions

The coordinated and integrated implementation of the e-government process and the e-government policy in Romania is absolutely necessary, as well as the reduction of bureaucracy. In this sense, in Romania, the Committee for e-government and bureaucracy reduction was established as a mechanism for decision and monitoring of the implementation of public policy, chaired and coordinated by the Prime Minister of Romania. Digitization remains one of the key priorities of the Romanian Government, along with simplifying legislation and improving the quality of regulations to support the business environment, both subscribed to targets constantly assumed by national strategies adopted and before the European Commission.

In conclusion, the evolution of e-government allows the inventory of the main services offered in the world to citizens and organizations. Moreover, basic public services have been defined at EU level, the implementation of which is crucial for comparing the progress of e-government in the Member States. The modernization of the public service, in order to

increase the efficiency and the capacity to face the needs, will be essentially based on information and communication technology, especially in the next period.

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